

Marco Nievergelt: Response to Draft chapter by Liz Eva Leach and Jonathan Morton :

It strikes me that there are multiple media here: the written word; the sung word/music; and the Manuscript. These provide complementary opportunities for 'experiencing' the text:

- Linguistic/verbal (but silent)
- oral/aural
- and visual

Q1: I get that "in this sense, the "work concept" of a medieval written text is more akin to that pointed to by a musical score than it is to a modern printed book ». But why does the failure of 'song' prompt a renewed attempt at persuasion 'in prose'? This seems counterintuitive...

cf Note 16 "we are convinced that the Bestiaire is 'a prose lyric'" > How exactly? Why? Is it really a lyric? Would it not be more accurate to say that it is a poetic text in prose (lyric implies verse, and metre, and music / singing...). I also don't really get the point that "The Bestiaire d'amours is preoccupied with the absent presence of textual performance, its script is preoccupied with sound, its prose (is preoccupied) with lyric". I'm not sure I understand what is meant by "lyric", and why that is a useful or necessary term in the discussion.

Context for Q2: I was a little struck by the comparative lack of forays into the intellectual environment in which Fournival moved (sources, existing debates, convergence, resonances, etc. with anything from medicine to developments in music or in Aristotle commentaries...) – particularly because he is, as you say at the beginning, a polymath. How does his text participate in larger intellectual and cultural 'movements' or 'developments', and can we 'situate' the text a little bit more precisely beyond what is quite a vague appeal to its 'performative character', and the implication that it may have been performed in a courtly setting?

Q2: On the relation of 'escrit' > 'parole' > 'painture' and >> 'presence' (the relation of the first two to 'painture' is not entirely clear to me from Fournival's prose...). Performance of a text means restoring written words to their 'natural' state, i.e. as spoken words, bringing those to life; the spoken/performed words in turn conjure up the 'image' or concept, making it vivid and 'alive' through the 'presence' and 'EXPERIENCE' of the spoken word. The idea of the 'Story of Troy' conjuring up its image etc. (>> what is the relation between 'oir' and 'entendre??') >> Quintilian and *energeia*, of course... But is there an echo here of Aristotle's seminal model of the 'semantic triangle' of the *Peri Hermeneias* / *De Interpretatione* 16a3–9 (which really is the key passage that triggers the entire tradition of medieval discussions of semantics and signification):

Now spoken sounds are symbols of affections in the soul, and written marks symbols of spoken sounds. And just as written marks are not the same for all men, neither are spoken sounds. But what these are in the first place signs of—affections of the soul—are the same for all; and what these affections are likenesses of—actual things—are also the same. These matters have been discussed in the work on the soul and do not belong to the present subject [cf. *De Anima* III.5–8]

“ The individual speaking or writing this particular text seems to merge with the text and with a textual tradition that the *Bestiaire d’amours* represents as a kind of collective memory of things past (such as Troy). « But is it really about Memory ? Is it not more of an act where the author “writes himself into existence”, or at least “into the presence” of the Lady, in a nearly ‘embodied’ fashion? But I am still unclear as to why prose is chosen (by Fournival) over song/lyric – which seems both more performative and more corporeal/sensual.

« In the reality of this work’s performance, the *vous* would have been a second-person plural, addressing the mixed-sex group of nobles listening to it as part of courtly leisure or entertainments at some kind of special event » Yes, I can see how this would probably have been the case: but then this raises some questions about the aims of the poem: what are they – beyond the relatively shallow self-promotion / writing into existence/presence of the speaking “je” through a putative appeal to a (fictional) lady’s attentions? Is it ‘play’ of some kind – but then what is the larger (anthropological, as it were) function of that play / performance? And why make it about animals and desire?